

APPENDIX A

PARAMETER DERIVATION OF THE EAL MODEL

A. Liquid-Solid

The heat transfer between the liquid layer and the solid layer can be expressed by a first order differential equation in (A.1).

$$Q^e - Q^y - Q^s = (c^e m^e + c^l m^l) \frac{dT^e}{d\tau} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

There are four terms in (A.1). The 4th term is associated with the temperature variation of the liquid layer. c^e is the specific heat capacity of the electrolytic bath, c^l is the specific heat capacity of liquid aluminum, m^e is the quality of the electrolytic bath and m^l is the quality of liquid aluminum. The first 3 terms describe the electrical power provided to the electrolyte cell, heat for electrochemical reactions and heat transfer to the solid layer. They are presented as follows:

$$Q^e = (U^e - E^e) I^e$$

$$Q^y = k^y \eta I^e (E^r + E^h)$$

$$Q^s = (T^e - T^s)(h^e A^e + h^l A^l + h^c A^c)$$

In the above, U^e is the cell voltage, E^e is the cell counter electromotive force, k^y is the yield coefficient, η is the current efficiency, E^r is the enthalpy of aluminum electrolysis reaction, E^h is the enthalpy of aluminum heating, h^e is the convective heat transfer coefficient between the electrolytic bath and the crust, h^l is the convective heat transfer coefficient between liquid aluminum and the crust, h^c is the convective heat transfer coefficient between the electrolytic bath and the anode, A^e is the heat transfer area between the electrolytic bath and the crust, A^l is the heat transfer area between liquid aluminum and the crust and A^c is the heat transfer area between the electrolytic bath and the anode.

As a result, (A.1) is simplified in (A.2).

$$\frac{dT^e}{d\tau} = \frac{1}{C^e} \left[H^e (T^s - T^e) + k^e I^e \right] \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where

$$C^e = c^e m^e + c^l m^l, H^e = h^e A^e + h^l A^l + h^c A^c,$$

$$k^e = (U^e - E^e) - (k^y \eta (E^r + E^h))$$

B. Solid-Air

Similarly, the heat transfer between the solid layer and the chamber air can be expressed in (A.3).

$$Q^s - Q^a = c^s m^s \frac{dT^s}{d\tau} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

In the above, c^s the specific heat capacity of the solid layer, m^s is the quality of the solid layer and Q^a is heat transfer to the chamber air which is shown as follows:

$$Q^a = (T^s - T^a) h^s A^s$$

In the above, h^s is the convective heat transfer coefficient between the solid layer and the chamber air and A^s is the heat transfer area between the solid layer and the chamber air. Therefore, (A.3) is simplified in (A.4).

$$\frac{dT^s}{d\tau} = \frac{1}{C^s} \left[H^s T^e - (H^s + H^e) T^s + H^s T^a \right] \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where

$$C^s = c^s m^s, H^s = h^s A^s$$

APPENDIX B

TRANSFORMED CT BI-LEVEL DR MODEL

The overall scheduling horizon H is divided into several periods with the time length T and the BP spline is implemented for each period.

A. Upper Level

The upper-level optimization are transformed into (B.1)-(B.4)

$$\min \sum_i \sum_t \left(c_i^{su} S_{i,t}^u + c_i^{sd} S_{i,t}^d + \mathbf{1}^T \mathbf{C}_{i,t}^{\text{f},\text{B}} / 4 \right) \left(\lambda_{i,t}^{\text{dr},\text{B}} \right)^T \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{dr},\text{B}} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$\sum_i [\mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{g},\text{B}} + \mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{wd},\text{B}}] = \sum_i [\mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{ld},\text{B}} + \mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{al},\text{B}}] \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$G(\mathbf{J} \mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{g},\text{B}}, S_{i,t}^u, S_{i,t}^d) \leq 0 \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$|\sum_i \text{SJ}[\mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{g},\text{B}} + \mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{wd},\text{B}} - (\mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{ld},\text{B}} + \mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{al},\text{B}})]| \leq f \quad (\text{B.4})$$

where $S_{i,t}^{(\cdot)}$ means the binary variables of $S_i^{(\cdot)}(\tau)$ in period τ . The binary commitment variables of thermal units are assumed to be constant in each time period. $[\ast]_{i,t}^{(\cdot),\text{B}}$ indicates the Bernstein coefficient vector of the continuous-time variable $[\ast]_i^{(\cdot)}(\tau)$ in period τ . In order to maintain continuity between the adjacent periods projected on the function space, the constraint (B.5) is imposed.

$$[\ast]_{i,t}^{(\cdot),\text{B},3} = [\ast]_{i,t+1}^{(\cdot),\text{B},0}, [\ast]_{i,t}^{(\cdot),\text{B},3} - [\ast]_{i,t}^{(\cdot),\text{B},2} = [\ast]_{i,t+1}^{(\cdot),\text{B},1} - [\ast]_{i,t+1}^{(\cdot),\text{B},0} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

B. Lower Level

The lower-level optimization are reformulated as

$$\max \sum_i \sum_t \left[\left(\lambda_{i,t}^{\text{dr},\text{B}} \right)^T \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{dr},\text{B}} + k_i^{\text{al}} \mathbf{1}^T \mathbf{Y}_{i,t}^{\text{al},\text{B}} / 4 - k_i^{\text{op}} (\mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{dr},\text{B}})^T \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{dr},\text{B}} \right] \quad (\text{B.6})$$

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{T}_{i,t}^{\text{e},\text{B}} - \mathbf{T}_{i,t,\text{ini}}^{\text{e},\text{B}} = \mathbf{L}^T (a_{1,i} \mathbf{T}_{i,t}^{\text{e},\text{B}} + a_{2,i} \mathbf{T}_{i,t}^{\text{s},\text{B}} + a_{3,i} \mathbf{I}_{i,t}^{\text{e},\text{B}}) \\ T_{i,t,\text{ini}}^{\text{e},\text{B},k} |_{t=1} = T_i^{\text{e}0}, T_{i,t,\text{ini}}^{\text{e},\text{B},k} |_{t>1} = T_{i,t-1,\text{ini}}^{\text{e},\text{B},3} \\ \mathbf{T}_{i,t}^{\text{s},\text{B}} - \mathbf{T}_{i,t,\text{ini}}^{\text{s},\text{B}} = \mathbf{L}^T (a_{4,i} \mathbf{T}_{i,t}^{\text{e},\text{B}} + a_{5,i} \mathbf{T}_{i,t}^{\text{s},\text{B}} + a_{6,i} \mathbf{T}_{i,t}^{\text{a},\text{B}}) \\ T_{i,t,\text{ini}}^{\text{s},\text{B},k} |_{t=1} = T_i^{\text{s}0}, T_{i,t,\text{ini}}^{\text{s},\text{B},k} |_{t>1} = T_{i,t-1,\text{ini}}^{\text{s},\text{B},3} \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_{i,t}^{\text{al},\text{B}} = k_i^y \eta \mathbf{I}_{i,t}^{\text{e},\text{B}} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{e},\text{B}} = N_i U_i^e \mathbf{T}_{i,t}^{\text{e},\text{B}} \\ \mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{e},\text{B}} + \mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{dr},\text{B}} = \mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{al},\text{B}} \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.9})$$

$$\underline{I}_i \leq \mathbf{J} \mathbf{I}_{i,t}^{\text{e},\text{B}} \leq \overline{I}_i, \underline{R}_i \leq \mathbf{J} \mathbf{W} \mathbf{P}_{i,t}^{\text{e},\text{B}} \leq \overline{R}_i, T_i \leq \mathbf{J} \mathbf{T}_{i,t}^{\text{e},\text{B}} \leq \overline{T}_i \quad (\text{B.10})$$

where $[\ast]_{i,t,\text{ini}}^{(\cdot),\text{B}}$ is the initial value of $[\ast]_{i,t}^{(\cdot),\text{B}}$ in period t . Note that the continuity constraint like (B.5) is also considered in the lower-level optimization.